

Viscosity Studies of Dilute Solutions of Lithium Iodide, Ammonium Iodide, and Tetrabutylⁿammonium Iodide in Butanolⁿ

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Viscosities of solutions of LiI, NH₄I, and (C₄H₉)₄NI in butanolⁿ at 0°, 25°, and 50° are reported. A plot of $(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c}$ vs. $\sqrt{c}$ at all temperatures show deviation from linearity. This deviation becomes more pronounced at very low concentrations and at low temperatures. The results are discussed briefly.

During the course of the study of conductances of dilute solutions of LiI, NH₄Iⁿ, and (C₄H₉)₄NIⁿ in butanolⁿ, it was considered desirable to measure the viscosities of these solutions at 0°, 25°, and 50° in order to evaluate the effect of viscosity on the limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) and on the ion-pair dissociation constant (K).

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagent grade butanolⁿ was refluxed for several hours with lime and distilled three times. In the final distillation the fraction boiling between 117.3° and 117.5° under atmospheric pressure was collected and used. The purified solvent had a refractive index of 1.3992. The dielectric constant, calculated according to the circular of the U.S. National Bureau of Standards³, is 20.44 at 0°, 17.10 at 25°, and 14.10 at 50°. The viscosities at different temperatures, reported in the literature, are: 0.05186 poise at 0°⁴; 0.0246 poise at 25°⁵; 0.01411 poise at 50°^{4,5}; these values check well with the extrapolated values of viscosity-temperature functions of liquids found in the literature⁶.

LiI, 3H₂O from the Mallinkrodt Chemical Works was purified by an anion-exchange process and was prepared in the anhydrous form as described elsewhere¹. The purity of the salt was better than 99.96%.

Reagent grade NH₄I was purified by an anion-exchange process^{1,2}. Analysis showed the purity of the salt to be 99.98%. Extra pure (C₄H₉)₄NI from Eastman Organic Chemicals was purified as described elsewhere².

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1. Venkatesetty and Brown, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 2075.

2. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, **67**, 954.

3. National Bureau of Standards, Circular No. 514, 1954.

4. "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 40th ed., Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., Cleveland, Ohio, 1958, p. 2158.

5. "International Critical Tables," Vol. 7, McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, N.Y., 1929, p. 41.

6. Nissan, *Phil. Mag.*, 1941, **32**, 441.

All solutions were prepared in a dry box under a positive pressure of dry nitrogen and the concentrations were established by analysis.

The viscosity determinations were carried out according to the recommendations and standards set forth by the American Society for Testing Materials⁷. Two viscosimeters were used in the work. The change in the viscometer constant with temperature was computed by the method recommended by Cannon and Fenske⁸. The timing devices used were spring-operated stopwatches which could be read to the nearest 0.05 sec. Their accuracy was checked against time signals broadcast by the National Bureau of Standards Station in Washington, D.C.

Temperature Control.—The viscosity measurements at 25° and 50° were made in a water bath equipped with a mercury thermoregulator and relay. The bath was capable of holding a temperature to $\pm 0.02^\circ$. The temperature was observed with a Beckmann thermometer which was calibrated against a thermometer certified by National Bureau of Standards. Determinations at 0° were made in the usual manner in a well-stirred, ice-water bath.

FIG. 1. Tetrabutyl¹ ammonium iodide in BuOH^a.

FIG. 2. Ammonium iodide in BuOH^a.

DISCUSSION

Viscosity, the force required to produce unit rate of shear between two layers separated by unit distance, is an important property of liquids. It is known that the electrical forces between ions in adjacent layers of an electrolyte solution will increase the viscosity. For the solutions of electrolytes, the relative viscosity, $\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$, is often used.

7. "Book of ASTM Standards," Designation D445-53T, ASTM Part V., 1955.

8. *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1938, 10, 297.

where η_0 denotes the viscosity of the pure solvent and η , the viscosity of the solution. Jones and Dole⁹ pointed out that the viscosities of the solutions of many salts could be accurately represented by the equation:

$$\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity, c is the concentration in moles per litre, and A and B are constants. Jones and Fornwalt¹⁰ measured the viscosities of dilute solutions of KI, KCl, KBr, and NH_4Cl in methanol at 25° and found that for these solutions the Jones and Dole equation was valid only up to a certain concentration. To test whether the Jones and Dole equation is applicable to the present data, a plot of $(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c}$ versus $\sqrt{c}$ was made. Deviations from linearity become apparent (see Figs. 1-3). At low concentrations the value of $(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c}$ decreases rapidly with increase of concentration. It passes through a minimum and levels off at 0° and 25° , whereas at 50° the plots approach linearity. The deviations observed in the present work are also observed^{9,11} for several salt solutions in water.

FIG. 3. LiI soln. in BuOH¹⁰.

In this study it has been found that the negative curvatures for the viscosity-concentration curves at low concentrations are general ones and become more pronounced at very low concentrations and also at low temperatures; this behaviour had been observed previously¹¹. There seems to be no satisfactory explanation for this phenomenon. The

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950.

10. *Ibid.*, 1936, 57, 2041.

11. Applebey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2000.

explanation given by Rabinovich¹² is that water and alcohols contain associated molecules which dissociate into simple molecules on introduction of soluble substances; the temperature also has marked influence on the dissociation process. This depolymerisation (dissociation) process gives rise to a net decrease in viscosity or a negative slope of the viscosity-concentration curves. The presence of the free ions and the undissociated molecules (ion pairs) of the systems investigated^{11,2} tend to increase the viscosity of the solution. In the solutions, reported in this investigation, the increase of viscosity due to the friction of the ions on the solvent molecules is probably less than the diminution of the viscosity due to the depolymerisation of butanol¹³, giving a negative slope of the viscosity concentration curve.

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